

Statistical Study of Blood Cancer (Leukemia) for the Period (1991-2006) in the Governorates of Southern Iraq (Basrah-Dhi Qar – Maysan)

Ammar Muslim Salih Alghurabi

Assistant Lecturer at Ministry of Education, General Directorate of Education, Nasiriyah, Dhi Qar, Iraq.

Email Address:

Correspondence should be addressed to alghurabiammar@gmail.com

Received: 31 Oct 2020, Revised: 11 Nov 2020, Accepted: 30 Nov 2020, Online: 30 Nov 2020

Abstract

Cancer: A group of diseases characterized by aggressive cells (undetermined growth and division), and the ability of these dividing cells to invade and destroy adjacent tissues, or move to distant tissues in a process called transfer. These abilities are the characteristics of malignancy unlike the benign tumor, which is characterized by specific growth and the inability to invade and does not have the ability to move or transfer. The benign tumor can develop into malignant cancer at times. **Purpose of the Study:** To promote the state of health awareness among citizens against leukemia and sedation, in order to take preventive measures to control the disease and reduce the rates of infection. **Materials and Methods:** Selection of a Random Sample from the Iraqi Local Community in Dhi Qar Governorate, Basrah and Maysan The sample size was 50 persons of both sexes. The average age (14-45 years) The educational level (primary - after university) After coding the data, the statistical analysis program SPSS, Word 2010 and Excel 2010 were used to analyze the questionnaire data and determine the validity and consistency of this questionnaire by using the Crombach Alpha test for the purpose of adopting the questionnaire on the level of awareness of leukemia. **Results:** 1). Analyzing the results of the questionnaire using the statistical analysis program SPSS and Excel 2010, the results showed that the health awareness of the risk of leukemia exceeded 50% for the local community in Basra, Dhi Qar & Maysan. 2) Leukemia increases due to early detection of symptoms of both children and adults and leukemia is the second most common type of breast cancer in females. 3) During the period from 1991 to 2006, the incidence of the 10 most cancers in southern Iraq (Basra, Diyala and Maysan) increased due to war, environmental pollution and sites contaminated with radioactive uranium.

Keywords: Leukemia, Acute Lymphoblastic, Leukemia, Acute Myeloid, Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia, Chronic Myeloid Leukemia

1. Introduction

Cancer is a group of diseases whose cells are hostile (growth and division of the unspecified), the ability of these divided

cells to invade and destroy adjacent tissues, or to move to distant tissues in a process called metastatic. These abilities

are the characteristics of a malignant tumor unlike a benign tumor, which is characterized by specific growth, inability to invade and not the ability to move or transport. A benign tumor can also develop into sometimes malignant cancer. Cancer can affect all age levels in humans up to embryos, but increases the risk of developing it as you age. Cancer causes death at 13% of all deaths. The American Cancer Society (ACS) points to the deaths of 7.6 million people worldwide in 2007. As cancer affects humans, forms of it affect both animals and plants. The conversion of healthy cells to cancerous cells is mostly due to changes in the embryonic material (gene).

These changes can be caused by carcinogens such as smoking, radiation, chemicals or infectious diseases (e.g. virus infection). There are also encouraging factors for cancer, such as a random error or mutation in the Deoxyribonucleic acid (**DNA**) version when the cell is split, or because of the inheritance of this error or mutation from the mother cell.

Research Problem

The medical and radiological tests carried out months after the end of the war in 2003 proved the existence of new diseases, especially in areas that were in direct contact with the war sites and its remnants that were thrown to the bottom of the river, and hospitals in southern Iraq witnessed an alarming rise in the incidence of leukemia.

Global reports conducted jointly with the World Health Organization and Environmental Protection confirmed that the environment in Iraq is contaminated and that there are more than 143 sites contaminated with uranium in 7 governorates, including 16 sites contaminated with uranium in Diyala Governorate, more than 20 sites in Babil, 11 sites in Wasit, and 14 sites in Maysan, 22 sites in Basra, 20 sites in Nasiriyah, and more than 40 contaminated sites in

Baghdad. The absence of prevention of cancerous diseases has contributed greatly to the high incidence of infection, and the majority of cases are diagnosed in late stages that are not treatable even by the best available means. There must be a link between treatment and early detection methods by educating the citizen and health workers. Cancer cases doubled immediately after the war. Strange cases that were not known before 1990 have emerged. There are about 160,000 Iraqis with cancer and cryptorchidomas, the majority of whom are young children, of whom more than 8,000 patients die annually, due to their weak bodies, lack of medicines, or delay in diagnosis due to the lack of medical staff. Currently operating specialist and modern hospitals equipped with the latest devices targeted for cancer treatment.

Importance of Research

1. Increasing the percentage of cancers spreading in Iraq with an increase in the percentage of deaths due to cancers.
2. Early detection, correct diagnosis of the disease and appropriate treatment help to give positive results by reducing the mortality rates of cancer.
3. Low level of society to the culture of awareness of the risks of mental and material cancers for the patient, family and society in general.
4. This research is a new addition to the library of various cancers.

Hypotheses

1. Are all types of tumors cancerous?
2. Is the statistical function hypothesis able to determine the validity of the data from the health education questionnaire against leukemia?
3. What are the statistics for the ten most common cancers in southern Iraq in particular?
4. A questionnaire about leukemia, prepared by the researcher.

Methodology

An experimental approach using the Individual Case Experience model.

The Limits of Spatial and Temporal Search

The research includes studying statistics on the most common cancers in southern Iraq

(Basra, Dhi Qar and Maysan) for the period from 1991 to 2006.

The research targeted a random sample of 50 persons from 3 governorates, by answering the questionnaire questions.

Tools

- 1- Designing a questionnaire form for leukemia (prepared by the researcher)
- 2- An interview guide for families of people with leukemia (prepared by the researcher)
- 3- A guide to interviewing experts, specialists and workers in the field of leukemia (prepared by the researcher)
- 4- Books, publications, periodicals, governmental and international organizations statistics in the field of leukemia in Iraq from 1990 to 2006.
- 5- Using the statistical analysis program SPSS 22 and the Word and Excel 2010 program.

The Aim of the Research

Enhancing the state of health awareness among citizens against leukemia and its varieties, in order to take preventive measures in order to control this disease and reduce the rates of infection with it.

Objectives

1. Promote concepts of leukemia and ways to prevent disease.
2. Know the methods of early diagnosis of the disease and the symptoms of the disease, and how to treat the three

negatives, chemotherapy, radiotherapy and surgical treatment.

3. Adopting real attitudes among healthy people in general and patients in particular to the degree of awareness of the causes of the disease and the means to reduce the incidence of leukemia.

Literature Reference

Blood consists of three types of cells floating in a fluid called plasma. These cellular components are:

1. Red blood cells ("Erythrocytes") - the cells that carry oxygen.
2. White blood cells ("Leukocytes") - cells that help form the body's immune system.
3. Platelets ("Thrombolytic") - cells that play an important role in forming blood clots.

The total number of white blood cells usually ranges from 4,000 to 11,000 cells per milliliter of blood. [1]

There are five types of leukocytes (white blood cells) found in the blood:

Basophils, eosinophil's, lymphocytes. Monocytes, neutrophils

Each type of cell has a specific role to play in the body's immune system. The important general functions of the immune system include:

- Defend against some invaders.
- Removing dead or damaged cells.
- Destruction of cancer cells.

Hematopoietic Stem Cells

Unlike most cells, hematopoietic stem cells and (stem cells in general) have the ability to self-renew, as well as the ability to give any one of the separate blood cell types.

This means that with stem cells dividing into two, one cell replaces the original stem cell, and the other initiates a multi-step process of development into mature blood cells.

It is important to note that hematopoietic stem cells are different from embryonic stem cells. While hematopoietic stem cells can develop into any type of blood cell, embryonic stem cells can develop into any type of cell in the whole body.

Precursor blood cells usually progress through a series of stages in the bone marrow before entering the circulating bloodstream. Signals from surrounding cells in the bone marrow can help stimulate stem cells to divide as well as develop and mature into specific blood cell types. Regular cell division also regulates an important process known as the cell cycle. Disruption of this process is pivotal in the development of leukemia. [4]

In the same way a family tree can be divided into bloodlines, and divided into five types of leukocytes (white blood cells) into two groups (lineages), based on how they are prepared. It includes myeloid cells, monocytes, neutrophils, eosinophils and basophils. Lymphocytes include B lymphocytes, T lymphocytes, and natural killer (NK) cells.

Cancer Blood (leukemia): It is a group of diseases characterized by increased numbers of white cells in the blood and bone marrow. [2]

In 2016, the American Cancer Society estimates that 60,140 new cases of leukemia will be diagnosed and 24,400 people will die from this disease in the United States. [3]

Leukemia is classified into 4 main categories, based on the type of white blood cells affected (lymphoid versus myeloid) and the characteristics of the disease (acute versus chronic):

1. Acute lymphocytic leukemia.
2. Acute myeloid leukemia (acute Myelogenous leukemia).
3. Chronic lymphocytic leukemia (chronic lymphocytic leukemia).
4. Chronic myeloid leukemia (chronic Myelogenous leukemia).

Acute leukemia: It is an aggressive disease in which metastases occur in the early stages of development of damaged blood cells. If not treated, these diseases can be rapidly fatal. [2]

Acute leukemia: is caused by damage to stem cells or cells in the early stages of growth in the bone marrow. Mutations that affect control of cell division, differentiation, and cell death lead to the accumulation of early precursors in blood cells known as blast cells. [2]

1. **Acute leukemia:** It is most common among children. [6] The incidence of acute leukemia in children aged (3-7) decreases by 10 years of age, and rises again after the age of 40. [7]
2. **Acute myeloid leukemia:** It represents 10-15% of leukemia diagnosed in childhood, and it is the most common type of acute leukemia diagnosed in adults. (8)
Chronic Leukemia: It is characterized by a slower progression of acute leukemia. This leukemia is more difficult to treat, so the treatment approach is often conservative and aims to control symptoms. [5]
3. **Chronic Lymphocytic Leukemia:** It is a disease characterized by the accumulation of fully developed B or T lymphocytes in the blood. Which accumulate in lymphocytes, lymph nodes and blood vessels? [9], by far the most common type of chronic lymphocytic leukemia, involve lymphocytes B. This disease mainly affects elderly

individuals, with a peak between 60 and 80 years of age. Age. [9]. It is the most common form of leukemia in western countries. [10], as it follows a variable course, with a survival period ranging from months to decades. [10] Other types of chronic lymphocytic leukemia include .[9]

4. **Chronic myeloid leukemia:** It is a disorder of the hematopoietic stem cells. This disease, which accounts for about 15% of leukemia, occurs most often between the ages of 40 and 60. Laboratory tests reveal an increase in the number of cells belonging to the myeloid line (monocytes, neutrophils, basophils, eosinophils) at various stages of development flowing into the bloodstream. .[5]

Risk Factors

Although the cause of leukemia in most patients is unknown, several factors are associated with an increased risk of developing the disease. Factors that affect the risk of developing leukemia include:

1. Age
2. Ethnicity /Gender
3. Inherited syndromes (e.g. Down syndrome)
4. Ionic radiation
5. Infection by certain viruses
6. Smoking cigarettes
7. The relative effects of these and other risk factors in any particular case of cancer are variable. Some of these and other risk factors are below.

1. Age

The risk of developing most types of leukemia increases steadily with age. However, the most common age groups for developing acute lymphocytic leukemia are between 3-7 years old and also after the age of 40.

[11] Acute childhood leukemia peaks without knowing the cause.

2. Chemotherapy

There is a subgroup of acute myeloid leukemia, "myeloid leukemia therapy associated", which can develop after treatment with chemotherapy. Although the causal relationship implies the name, the exact mechanism is still unknown. [12], the prognosis for secondary acute myeloid leukemia is generally unfavorable compared to primary myeloid leukemia. [8]

3. Ethnicity / Gender

With the exception of CML, which has a similar incidence in whites and blacks, leukemia occurs more commonly in those white lineage compared to those of Asian, Hispanic and black descent. Leukemia also occurs more frequently in males than females. [11]

4. Inherited syndromes

Children with Down syndrome have approximately 20 times the increased risk of developing leukemia in childhood compared to children without Down syndrome. [13], about 10% of children with Down syndrome are born with "transient leukemia" that resolves. Spontaneously within months of birth. Only one to two percent, however, develop acute malignant leukemia that requires chemotherapy by the age of four. [14] While several hypotheses have been proposed, the cause of this increased risk remains uncertain. Other inherited syndromes that increase the risk of developing leukemia include:

- Ataxia - telangiectasia [15]
- Bloom's syndrome
- Fanconi syndrome [16]
- Klinefelter syndrome [17]

An increase in leukemia was observed among survivors of the atomic bombing of Japanese cities. Although the risks associated with low-level radiation exposure are not clear, studies have shown an increase in leukemia after using radiotherapy for ankylosing spondylitis (a form of arthritis) and exposure to diagnostic X-rays of the fetus during pregnancy. [18]

5. Viruses

Infection in human is associated with a T-cell lymphoma virus (HTLV-I) associated with the development of adult T cells leukemia / lymphoma (ATLL), a mature T-cell activated lymphoma. [19]. Data from cancer records in Japan indicate that the lifetime risk of developing hepatitis C among those infected is 2.1 percent for females and 6.6 percent for males. [20]

Symptoms

Leukemia results in the accumulation of cancer cells in the bone marrow and blood.

The presence of large numbers of abnormal cells in the bone marrow can prevent the marrow from producing normal healthy blood cells. Symptoms from bone marrow failure include paleness, fatigue, and shortness of breath, excessive bleeding, and increased susceptibility to infections. Cancer cells can also infiltrate organs such as the lymph nodes, spleen, and liver, leading to swelling. [21]

Treatment

Leukemia treatments include the following, immunotherapy (chemotherapy), radiation therapy, stem cell transplantation and surgery.

3. Materials and Tools

The study sample: - Selecting a random sample from the Iraqi community in the

governorates of Dhi Qar, Basra and Maysan. The sample size is 50 persons of both sexes. The average age is from (14-45 years), the educational level (primary - post-university).

Questionnaire

16 Questions are as Follows: -

1. Do you know what leukemia means?
2. Is leukemia a serious disease?
3. Is leukemia contagious?
4. Is leukemia related to genetics?
5. What are the most vulnerable age groups to developing leukemia?
6. From the following factors, choose what you think may be the cause of leukemia?
7. What are the symptoms that you expect to appear on a patient who suffers from leukemia?
8. Does leukemia have complications on other body parts?
9. What are the organs of the human body most affected by complications from leukemia?
10. In your view, which of the following complications may accompany leukemia?
11. Which of these procedures may help in treating leukemia?
12. Are there medications for leukemia?
13. Which of these measures may help in treating leukemia?
14. Can leukemia be treated with chemotherapy?
15. Can leukemia be treated with radiotherapy?
16. Is it possible to treat leukemia with a bone marrow transplant?

After coding the data, *the SPSS statistical analysis program* was used to analyze the questionnaire data and find out the validity and reliability of this questionnaire through the use of the *Cronbach Alpha program* for the purpose of adopting the questionnaire form for the degree of awareness of leukemia.

- Study the statistics of the ten most common cancers in Iraq in general and the southern regions in particular.

Test the reliability and validity of the questionnaire using the Cronbach alpha test

Notes

Output Created		28-AUG-2017 19:21:48
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\AM\Documents\Untitled2.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	189
	Matrix Input	
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data for all variables in the procedure.
Syntax		RELIABILITY /VARIABLES=Q1 Q2 Q3 Q4 Q5 Q8 Q9 Q10 Q11 Q12 Q13 Q14 Q15 Q16 /SCALE('ALL VARIABLES') ALL /MODEL=SPLIT /SUMMARY=TOTAL.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:00.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:00.02

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	40	21.2
	Excluded ^a	149	78.8
	Total	189	100.0

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	.698
		N of Items	7 ^a
	Part 2	Value	.765
		N of Items	7 ^b
Total N of Items			14
Correlation Between Forms			.951
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		.975
	Unequal Length		.975
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			.966

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Do you know what leukemia means?	18.1000	19.067	.000	.877
Is leukemia a serious disease?	18.1000	19.067	.000	.877
Is leukemia an infectious disease?	17.6750	15.558	.825	.849
Does leukemia have a genetic relationship?	17.9000	16.400	.763	.855
What more age groups are at risk of developing leukemia	16.6750	11.763	.878	.848
Does leukemia have complications on other body parts?	18.0750	18.584	.336	.874
What are the organs of the human body most affected by complications of leukemia?	18.0000	17.436	.606	.864
In your view, any of the following complications may accompany leukemia?	17.4000	14.862	.819	.846
Which of these procedures may help treat leukemia?	16.4500	11.382	.873	.853
Are there leukemia drugs?	18.0500	18.151	.461	.870
Which of these procedures may help treat leukemia?	18.1000	19.067	.000	.877
Is it possible to treat leukemia and chemotherapy?	18.1000	19.067	.000	.877
Is it possible to treat leukemia with radiotherapy?	17.8750	16.215	.785	.853
Can leukemia be treated with a bone marrow transplant?	17.8000	15.805	.825	.850

Notes

Output Created		28-AUG-2017 19:18:07
Comments		
Input	Data	C:\Users\AM\Documents\Untitled2.sav
	Active Dataset	DataSet1
	Filter	<none>
	Weight	<none>
	Split File	<none>
	N of Rows in Working Data File	189
Missing Value Handling	Definition of Missing	User-defined missing values are treated as missing.
	Cases Used	Statistics are based on all cases with valid data.
Syntax		FREQUENCIES VARIABLES=Q1 Q2 Q3 Q4 Q5 Q8 Q9 Q10 Q11 Q12 Q13 Q14 Q15 Q16 /STATISTICS=MINIMUM MAXIMUM MEAN /PIECHART PERCENT /ORDER=ANALYSIS.
Resources	Processor Time	00:00:04.03
	Elapsed Time	00:00:03.52

Statistics

		Do you know what leukemia means	Is leukemia a serious disease	Is leukemia an infectious disease	Does leukemia have a genetic relationship	What more age groups are at risk of developing leukemia
N	Valid	46	46	44	47	63
	Missing	143	143	145	142	126
Mean		1.1304	1.0652	1.4773	1.3191	3.0794
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00	5.00

Statistics

		Does leukemia have complications on other body parts	What are the most parts of the human body affected by complications from leukemia	In your view, any of the following complications may accompany leukemia	Which of these procedures may help treat leukemia	Are there medicines for leukemia
N	Valid	42	118	57	94	40
	Missing	147	71	132	95	149
Mean		1.0714	3.3390	2.5789	4.1702	1.0500
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		2.00	9.00	7.00	6.00	2.00

Statistics

		Which of these procedures can help treat leukemia?	Can leukemia be treated with chemotherapy?	Is it possible to treat leukemia with radiation therapy?	Can leukemia be treated with a bone marrow transplant
N	Valid	60	48	50	50
	Missing	129	141	139	139
Mean		1.2833	1.1042	1.3800	1.4400
Minimum		1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Maximum		3.00	2.00	2.00	2.00

Frequency Table
Do you know what leukemia means?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	22.8	93.5	93.5
	No	3	1.6	6.5	100.0
	Total	46	24.3	100.0	
Missing	System	143	75.7		
Total		189	100.0		

Is leukemia a serious disease?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	22.8	93.5	93.5
	No	3	1.6	6.5	100.0
	Total	46	24.3	100.0	
Missing	System	143	75.7		
Total		189	100.0		

Is leukemia an infectious disease?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Yes	23	12.2	52.3
	No	21	11.1	47.7
	Total	44	23.3	100.0
Missing	System	145	76.7	
Total		189	100.0	

Does leukemia have to do with genetics?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Yes	32	16.9	68.1
	No	15	7.9	31.9
	Total	47	24.9	100.0

Missing System	142	75.1	
Total	189	100.0	

What age groups are most at risk of developing leukemia?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Kids	10	5.3	15.9	15.9
	Youth	9	4.8	14.3	30.2
	Older persons	15	7.9	23.8	54.0
	Not limited to a certain age	24	12.7	38.1	92.1
	I don't know	5	2.6	7.9	100.0
	Total	63	33.3	100.0	
Missing System		126	66.7		
Total		189	100.0		

Does leukemia have complications on other organs?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	39	20.6	92.9	92.9
	No	3	1.6	7.1	100.0
	Total	42	22.2	100.0	
Missing System		147	77.8		
Total		189	100.0		

What organs of the human body are most affected by leukemia complications?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Heart	36	19.0	30.5	30.5
	Lung	16	8.5	13.6	44.1
	liver	21	11.1	17.8	61.9
	Bones	13	6.9	11.0	72.9
	Muscle	8	4.2	6.8	79.7
	Stomach	8	4.2	6.8	86.4
	Intestines	6	3.2	5.1	91.5
	Nerves	9	4.8	7.6	99.2
	Other than that	1	.5	.8	100.0
	Total	118	62.4	100.0	
Missing System		71	37.6		
Total		189	100.0		

Which of the following complications may accompany leukemia?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Appearance of immune diseases	15	7.9	26.3	26.3

	Decrease of antibodies	22	11.6	38.6	64.9
	Soft bone	13	6.9	22.8	87.7
	I don't know	7	3.7	12.3	100.0
	Total	57	30.2	100.0	
Missing	System	132	69.8		
	Total	189	100.0		

Which of these procedures can help treat leukemia?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Protection of the central nervous system	6	3.2	6.4	6.4
	The bone marrow transplant	15	7.9	16.0	22.3
	Increase fat intake	6	3.2	6.4	28.7
	Refrain from smoking	26	13.8	27.7	56.4
	Early focus in symptoms	12	6.3	12.8	69.1
	Early diagnosis	29	15.3	30.9	100.0
	Total	94	49.7	100.0	
Missing	System	95	50.3		
	Total	189	100.0		

Are there drugs for leukemia?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Yes	38	20.1	95.0
	No	2	1.1	5.0
	Total	40	21.2	100.0
Missing	System	149	78.8	
	Total	189	100.0	

Which of these procedures can help treat leukemia?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Intensive treatment	45	23.8	75.0
	Movement and exercise	13	6.9	21.7
	I don't know	2	1.1	3.3
	Total	60	31.7	100.0
Missing	System	129	68.3	
	Total	189	100.0	

Can leukemia be treated with chemotherapy?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	43	22.8	89.6	89.6
	No	5	2.6	10.4	100.0
	Total	48	25.4	100.0	
Missing	System	141	74.6		
Total		189	100.0		

Can leukemia be treated with a bone marrow transplant?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	28	14.8	56.0	56.0
	No	22	11.6	44.0	100.0
	Total	50	26.5	100.0	
Missing	System	139	73.5		
Total		189	100.0		

Table (1) The 10 most common cancers in Basra number of new cases by primary location, percentage of total cases and registered cases per 100,000 populations

No	location	Number of cases	Total percentage	Recorded cases per 100,000 inhabitants of the population
1	Breast cancer	263	18.25	14.04
2	Leukemia	121	8.40	6.46
3	Bladder cancer	93	6.46	4.96
4	Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma	90	6.25	4.80
5	Bronchial and lung cancer	74	5.14	3.95
6	Colorectal cancer	70	4.86	3.74
7	Cancer of the brain and central nervous system	55	3.82	2.94
8	Skin cancer	55	3.82	2.94
9	Stomach cancer	43	2.98	2.29
10	Throat cancer	41	2.85	2.19

11	Total of ten cancers	905	62.80	48.30
12	Total locations	1441	100.00	76.91

Table (2) population by sex in Basra, 2006

Sex The government	Number of men	Percentage %	Number of females	Percentage %	Total	Percentage %
Basra	943442	6.51	930200	6.50	1873642	6.50

Table (3) Top 10 cancers in Dhi Qar number of new cases by primary location, percentage of total cases and registered cases / 100,000 populations

Location	Number of cases	Total percent age	Recorded cases per 100,000 inhabitants of the population
Breast cancer	78	14.00	4.98
Leukemia	50	8.98	3.19
Bronchial and lung cancer	48	8.62	3.06
Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma	48	8.62	3.06
Bladder cancer	33	5.92	2.11
Hodkins disease	25	4.49	1.60
Cancer of the brain and central nervous system	20	3.59	1.28
Skin cancer	18	3.23	1.15
Stomach cancer	15	2.69	0.96
Ovarian cancer	14	2.51	0.89
Total of 10 cancers	349	62.66	22.27
Total locations	557	100.00	35.55

Table No (4) Population in Dhi Qar governorate by sex-2006

sex The government	Number of men	Percentage %	Number of females	Percentage %	Total	Percentage %
Dhi Qar	787677	5.43	779224	5.44	1566901	5.44

Table (5) The 10 most common cancers in Maysan Number of new cases by primary location, percentage of total and registered cases / 100,000 populations

	Location	Number of cases	Total percent age	Recorded cases per 100,000 inhabitants of the population
1	Breast cancer	49	11.69	6.10
2	Leukemia	40	9.55	4.98
3	Bronchial and lung cancer	38	9.07	4.73
4	Bladder cancer	35	8.35	4.36
5	Cancer of the brain and central nervous system	22	5.25	2.74
6	Cancer non-Hodgkin's disease	19	4.53	2.37
7	Skin cancer	17	4.06	2.12
8	Colorectal cancer	16	3.82	1.99
9	Stomach cancer	16	3.82	1.99
10	Hodgkins disease cancer	14	3.34	1.74
11	Total of 10 cancers	266	63.48	33.12
12	Total locations	419	100.00	52.16

Table (6) population in Maysan governorate by sex

sex	Number of men	Percentage %	Number of females	Percentage %	Total	Percentage %
The government						
Maysan	404021	2.79	399232	2.79	803253	2.79

4. Results

1. Analyzing the results of the survey using SPSS and Excel 2010, the results were that the percentage of health awareness of the risk of leukemia exceeded 50% for the local community in Basra, Dhi Qar and Maysan.
2. Blood cancer (leukemia) is increasing due to the lack of early detection of symptoms experienced by both children and adults and leukemia is second only to breast cancer in females .
3. From 1991 to 2006, the 10 most common cancers in the regions of southern Iraq (Basra, Dhi Qar and Maysan) increased due to wars, environmental pollution and the presence of radioactive uranium-contaminated sites.

5. Recommendations

1. The researcher recommends that the Iraqi Ministry of Health provide continuous health awareness programs for all types of cancers and strengthen cooperation with the community sector in this field.
2. The researcher recommends that the Iraqi Ministry of Health build specialized hospitals for cancer tumors and train medical and health cadres in order to reduce mortality rates in cancer patients while providing quality treatments from international hospitals and providing modern screening and treatment devices.

6. References

- [1]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition.

- Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 365.
- [2]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 157.
- [3]. American Cancer Society. Cancer Facts & Figures 2016. Atlanta: American Cancer Society; 2016. [http://www.cancer.org/acs/groups/content/@research/documents/document/acspc-047079.pdf]
- [4]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 9.
- [5]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 174.
- [6]. Stanulla M, Cario G, Meissner B, Schrauder A, Moricke A, Riehm H, Schrappe M. "Integrating molecular information into treatment of childhood acute lymphoblastic leukemia - A perspective from the BFM study group." *Blood Cells Mol Dis.* 2007 Sep-Oct; 39(2):160-3. Epub 2007 May 25.
- [7]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (Ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 158.
- [8]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (Ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 167.
- [9]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 188.
- [10]. Zhou GB, Li G, Chen SJ, and Chen Z. "From dissection of disease pathogenesis to elucidation of mechanisms of targeted therapies: leukemia research in the genomic era." *Acta Pharmacol Sin.* 2007 Sep; 28(9):1434-49.
- [11]. Yamamoto JF, Goodman MT. "Patterns of leukemia incidence in the United States by subtype and demographic characteristics, 1997-2002." *Cancer Causes Control.* 2007 Dec 7 [Epub ahead of print]
- [12]. Larson RA, "Etiology and management of therapy-related myeloid leukemia." *Hematology Am Soc Hematol Educ Program.* 2007; 2007:453-9.
- [13]. Alderton LE, Spector LG, Blair CK, Roesler M, Olshan AF, Robison LL, Ross JA. "Child and maternal household chemical exposure and the risk of acute leukemia in children with Down's syndrome: a report from the Children's Oncology Group." *Am J Epidemiol.* 2006 Aug 1; 164(3):212-21. Epub 2006 Jun 7.
- [14]. Izraeli S, Rainis L, Hertzberg L, Smooha G, Yehudit B. "Trisomy of chromosome 21 in leukemogenesis." *Blood Cells Mol Dis.* 2007 Sep-Oct; 39(2):156-9. Epub 2007 May 29.
- [15]. Armata HL, Garlick DS, Sluss HK. "The ataxia telangiectasia-mutated target site ser18 is required for p53-mediated tumor suppression." *Cancer Res.* 2007 Dec 15; 67(24):11696-703.
- [16]. Meyer S, Fergusson WD, Whetton AD, Moreira-Leite F, Pepper SD, Miller C, Saunders EK, White DJ, Will AM, Eden T, Ikeda H, Ullmann R, Tuerkmen S, Gerlach A, Klopocki E, Tonnes H. "AmplificationAlso: gene amplification. An abnormal process in which many copies of the same chromosome region are produced via DNA replication. The result can be a small 'microsatellite' chromosome or a region of DNA within a chromosome with many contiguous copies of a small set of genes. and translocation of 3q26 with overexpression of EVII in Fanconi anemia-derived childhood acute myeloid leukemia with biallelic FANCD1/BRCA2 disruption." *Genes Chromosomes Cancer.* 2007 Apr; 46(4):359-72.
- [17]. Swerdlow AJ, Schoemaker MJ, Higgins CD, Wright AF, Jacobs PA. "Cancer incidence and mortality in men with klinefelter syndrome: a cohort study." *J Natl Cancer Inst.* 2005 Aug 17; 97(16):1204-10.
- [18]. Boon et al. "Principles & Practice of Medicine." (20th edition) Churchill Livingstone, 2006. Pgs 1039-1047.
- [19]. Matutes E. "Adult T-cell leukaemia/lymphoma." *J Clin Pathol.* 2007 Dec; 60(12):1373-
- [20]. Taylor G. "Molecular aspects of HTLV-1 infection and adult T-cell leukaemia/lymphoma." *J Clin Pathol.* 2007 Dec; 60(12):1392-6.
- [21]. Hoffbrand AV, Moss PAH, Pettit JE (ed). "Essential Haematology" 5th Edition. Blackwell Publishing, Oxford: 2006. Pg. 159.
- [22]. Habsa A. A. Amshahar, Sana Taher Ashur. (2020). Evaluation of Knowledge among Libyan Women about Breast Cancer and its Risk Factors. *Journal of Global Scientific Research.* Vol.9. pp: 803-813.